

Variable Stiffness Composites for Morphing and Deployable Application

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Content

Introduction

» This research intends to investigate the concept of variable stiffness in laminated composite

» One main application of variable stiffness composites is in aerospace and space industries for deployable structures and morphing applications. Another application is in the emerging field of soft robotics

» **Variable stiffness** is the capability of altering the overall rigidity of a structure

» **Morphing** in engineering refers to continuous shape change upon activation in contrast to discrete parts moving relative to each other

Variable Stiffness Mechanism

Variable Stiffness - Changing Geometry

» Modification of shape leading to a change in the second moment of area while having the material properties unchanged. (Hayes et. al., 2015) and (Krishnan et al., 2015)

(1)

(2)

Figure. (1) The self-folding polymer sheet with multi hinges and (2) McKibben actuator with two families of fibres

Variable Stiffness - Altering Material Properties

- » Variable stiffness enabled by presence of SMA wires in a hybrid composite (SMAHC) plate. This can improve the overall structural response of the plate in terms of stiffness and strength at elevated temperatures

(1)

(2)

Figure. (1) Structure of a SMAHC plate and (2) stress–strain curve of the plate at ambient and elevated temperatures

Variable Stiffness - Hybrid

» Utilise the benefits of both geometrical reconfiguration and altering material properties to achieve controllable stiffness in a structure

Figure. A structure that incorporates variable stiffness cables and a moveable structure to facilitate the change in structural stiffness. (Zappetti et al., 2020)

Aim and Objectives

» Aim:

- To design and develop composite structures for morphing and deployable applications

» Objectives:

- To achieve a consistent laboratory manufacturing process for composite plates, incorporating the active layer
- To characterise the thermo-mechanical performance of these plates
- To characterise the electro-thermo-mechanical performance of these plates

- » Applying a strategy of thermoplastic softening
- » By combining two material systems with different T_g , a structure can be made in which the stiffness varies as a result of heating, either applied externally or generated internally

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Concept

- » Interleaving thermoplastic layer (lower T_g) in a system with higher T_g
- » The softening in the active layer will disrupt the shear stress transfer to the stacks and leading to stiffness reduction

A: The structure is rigid below the active layer T_g

B: It becomes compliant when the temperature is above the T_g of the active layer

Material Selection

Active layer material:

- » The active material should not cause thermal degradation of the base material
- » Softening effect occurs above room temperature
- » The active material should be sufficiently stiff that it will not cause an excessive reduction in stiffness of the structure

Base Material:

- » Stiff and light
- » High T_g in comparison to the active layer
- » Co-cured with the active layer

Material Selection

» Studied different thermoplastics in terms of T_g and modulus

» Finalised materials:

- **CFRP T_g at 170°C (onset of E')**
 - NTPT TP402/MR70 prepregs
- **PET T_g at 80°C (onset of E')**
 - GoodFellow Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) Film

Manufacturing – Passive Heating Sample

- » Hand layup and cure in the hot press at 6 bar
- » Layup configuration:
 - Control Sample: $[0^\circ_{60}]$
 - PET Sample: $[0^\circ_{30}/\text{PET}/ 0^\circ_{30}]$

Manufacturing – Active Heating Sample

- » 7 Copper wires were embedded between two layers of PET film
- » Hand layup to assemble the stack which was cured in the hot press at 6 bar
- » Layup configuration:
 - $[0^{\circ}_{10} / \text{PET} / \text{Copper wires} / \text{PET} / 0^{\circ}_{10}]$

Temperature contours of PET surface from Joule heating at 5A

Testing – Passive Heating

- » Three point bending test was used to obtain flexural stiffness
- » Samples were heated in the environmental chamber and loaded once the target temperature was reached
- » For both control and PET samples, the span-to-thickness ratio remained the same

Testing – Active Heating

- » To actuate the active interlayer, a constant current was applied using Joule heating
- » Samples were pre-heated using a range of current and time of heating
- » Samples were then loaded to obtain the flexural stiffness from three point bending test

Result and Discussion – Passive Heating

		Temperature (°C)	Stiffness reduction
Control Sample	C-RT	Room Temp.	-
	C-120	120°C	-17% relative to (C-RT)
	C-140	140°C	-24% relative to (C-RT)
Int. PET samples	P-RT	Room Temp.	-18% relative to (C-RT)
	P-120	120°C	-41% relative to (C-120)
	P-140	140°C	-49% relative to (C-140)

- » The PET led to a reduction in stiffness of 18% at room temperature
- » The effect of thermoplastic softening in PET was demonstrated at elevated temperature, where the upper and lower CFRP plies could slide relative to each other leading to a reducing in stiffness
- » Stiffness reduction of 41% and 49% was achieved in P-120 and P-140 respectively

Result and Discussion – Active Heating

Current (A)	Heating Time (s)	Stiffness (N/mm)	Stiffness reduction
0A	-	299.3	-
5A	10	298.5	-0.28%
5A	50	296.1	-1.08%
6A	10	296.9	-0.80%
6A	50	292.2	-2.39%
7A	10	296.0	-1.11%
7A	50	275.5	-7.95%
8A	10	297.6	-0.57%
8A	40	255.5	-14.63%

- » No significant stiffness reduction was observed from 5A or 6A
- » A stiffness reduction of 15% was achieved after pre-heating at 8A for a duration of 40s

Summary and Concluding Remarks

- » Investigated the concept of variable stiffness through thermo-mechanical and electro-thermo-mechanical analysis
- » Laminated composites with PET insert demonstrated the capability of variable stiffness
- » Passive heating above the T_g of PET resulted in a maximum of 50% stiffness reduction
- » The use of Joule heating resulted in a 15% stiffness reduction at a pre-heating time of 40 seconds at 8A

Thank you

Q & A

